

Greener Journal of Social Sciences

GJSS ISSN: 2276-7800 Impact Factor 2012 (UJRI): 0.7863 ICV 2012: 5.99

Response of Community towards Gender Dysphorics

By

Tahir farid
Madad Ali
Muhammad Shafeeq
Inayat Khattak

Research Article

Response of Community towards Gender Dysphorics

Tahir farid¹, Madad Ali², Muhammad Shafeeq³ and Inayat Khattak⁴

¹M.Phil scholar sociology department University of Peshawar

²M.Phil scholar sociology department Agriculture University Peshawar

³Lecturer in Philosophy Social work & Sociology Department Kohat University

⁴NRM coordinator, SRSP KARAK

Corresponding Author's Email: shahidanaveed@live.com

ABSTRACT

The present study was specially design to analyze the Response of Community towards Gender Dysphorics (hijras). The study of community attitudes towards gender dysphorics. Further it also examines the study of different aspect of Gender Dysphorics, social life and their social problems. It had three main parts; first their adjustment in their families and ignorance of their parents which increase the ratio of Gender Dysphorics in society. The second part focus on community attitude toward gender dysphorics, their perception and level of maturity; what is considered - the hijras.Would they accept their presence in society or not? What image is grown in their mind? It tells us how they adjust in that society with this spectacle of community. In the third part, it studies their socio-psycho problems which are the outcomes of difficulties in surviving. The data was collected by closed structure questionnaires. It mainly focused on community response, perceptions and attitudes toward them on the basis of purposive sampling. It would also tell the religio-cultural roles and support in society; whether or not they would support them like other individuals and try to discover the solution of their problems and, how it can be solved.

Key Words: Response, Community, Gender Dysphorics.

INTRODUCTION

The hijras are very traditional to gender in the society, they are mostly transgender (male convert to female or vice versa); the appearance of themselves create controversy between the individuals or among the sexes in society. Because in society, there is already conflict on roles and status between two sexes (male /female), so they are never ready to accept appearance of new sex (a third) and its new roles and status. This ignorance starts a new battlefield in the society because they try to find adjustment but they face maladjustment in society. Then they are confronted by ignorance, disrespect, isolation, etc from culture, religion as well as community. That negative attitude toward *khawaja saras* (hijras) create so many socio-psycho problems for them. The topic mainly focuses on community attitudes toward *khawaja saras* (third gender) and its effect or outcomes.

Hijra is a unique form of gender expressed in Pakistan where men behave like women; people refer to such individuals as behaving like "hijra", but not as women. The term hijra is often attributed as an abusive word to a man who is whimsical, womanly, effeminate, impotent or ineffective (Talwar, 1999). Large and ugly looking people, with big hands and feet, wearing high tone colours and makeup (beard is noticeable), emphasis on certain body parts (breasts, hips etc.), exaggerated movements and non verbal gestures including clapping, cracking obscene jokes, vulgar in talk and gestures etc; indeed these stereotype impressions developed about hijras over the ages.

Individuals who are born with sexual deformity (hermaphrodite or intersexed) are known as Khusra (a genuine Hijra). This is the identity which hijra strongly portray (Nanda, as cited in Sharma, 2000; Ali, 2003; Riaz, 1996). Hijra community claims the custody of child born with sexual deformity (Talwar, 1999; Sharma, 2000). According to Hijras (respondents in this research), they go for asking Wadhai (alms) after the child's birth actually to confirm child's sexual identity. In case of sexual deformity, they claim the custody by declaring that the child belongs to them. However, the possibility of their taking away the child forcibly is remote.

The myth widely believed is "born hijra (Khusra), develops akin mannerism (dancing, singing) acceptable in hijra community only. These born with sexual deformity ultimately join hijra community". It may not be true that all are born hijras; only about 1% of the whole hijra community are hermaphrodite or intersexed, others are transgender, cross-dressers, homosexuals or bisexuals.

Hijras are granted equal legal rights and obligations in the society. Hijras are denied any quota in employment on the basis of their handicap (where they have one) and also deprived of opportunities to take education because of people's attitude towards them. More so, they are also denied health and psychological/psychotherapeutic assistance. Victims of gender identity problem carry out castrations without any medical and psychological aid. They indulge in self-remedy including hormone taking without prescription, using silicone injections and at extreme auto-castrations. There is no one to understand them and find solution to their problems. People give away alms, but it is only because of the fear of curses and desire for good wishes. Asexuality and also certain behavioral patterns such as cracking vulgar jokes, using obscene language and throwing vulgar gestures, induce annoyance resulting in people harbouring negative attitude towards them. By and large, people do not like to interact with them. Humaira Jami (Research Associate)

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to discover community response towards hijras in the District of Kohat. The topic mainly focuses on khawaja Saras (hijra) which is one sort of third sex. The research was conducted on the community's response toward them. Their negative and positive spectacles, their opinions and attitudes towards hijras; the study seeks;

1. To know the attitude of community toward khawaja saras.
2. To know adjustment problems in their families face.
3. To know their socio-psycho problems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main purpose of the study was to discover community response towards hijras in the District of Kohat. The topic mainly focuses on khawaja saras (hijra) which is one sort of third gender. The research was conducted on the community's response toward them. Their negative and positive spectacles, their opinions and attitudes towards hijras, and to know how it influences on hijras life.

The research is so significant for the future researchers who conduct research on gender related phenomena. It also identifies gender discrimination and the appearance existence of new a gender in the society and describes its new roles and status. It is also beneficial for government, government welfare associations and, non-governmental organizations who try to know their problems and try to help them adjust in society and with their families. The research identified the violation of their rights and attempts to correct these violations. It also tries to create awareness about that third gender and try to clarify the confusion about them.

Non probability sampling method was followed in which purposive sampling techniques was used. The study was limited to the local community of District Kohat. The total number of population was 200. A sample of 40 respondents was taken by using survey sampling method. A comprehensive closed structured questionnaire was prepared for data collection from community.

Data Tabulation

Table 1: Showing interaction with hijras

Interaction	Frequency	Percent
Yes	18	45.0
No	22	55.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 2: Showing that these are normal individuals

Normal individuals	Frequency	Percent
Yes	14	35.0
No	26	65.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 3: Showing equal rights like other citizens

Equal rights	Frequency	Percent
Yes	30	75.0
No	10	25.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 4: Showing that they are in their neighborhood (they visit their homes)

Visit	Frequency	Percent
Yes	22	55.0
No	18	45.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 5: Showing that they want to take residency in their area

Residency in area	Frequency	Percent
Yes	22	55.0
No	18	45.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 6: Showing that they need anything

Need anything	Frequency	Percent
Yes	34	85.0
No	6	15.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 7: Showing that they are adjustable people

Adjustable people	Frequency	Percent
Yes	24	60.0
No	16	40.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 8: Showing that they participates in their burials

Participate in burials	Frequency	Percent
Yes	16	40.0
No	24	60.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 9: Showing that they have right to live a respectable life

Respectable life	Frequency	Percent
Yes	40	100.0

Table 10: Showing that they are deviant

Deviant	Frequency	Percent
Yes	22	55.0
No	18	45.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 11: Showing that they dance to fulfill their financial needs

Financial needs	Frequency	Percent
Yes	34	85.0
No	6	15.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 12: Showing that they have proper religion

Proper religion	Frequency	Percent
Yes	14	35.0
No	26	65.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 13: Showing their presence according to religious injunctions

Religious injunction	Frequency	Percent
Yes	14	35.0
No	26	65.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 14: Showing that they have lower status

Lower status	Frequency	Percent
Yes	32	80.0
No	8	20.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 15: Showing their negative effect on social environment

Negative effect	Frequency	Percent
Yes	32	80.0
No	8	20.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 16: Showing interest in solving their problems

Solving problems	Frequency	Percent
Yes	24	60.0
No	16	40.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 17: Showing when anybody teases they try to stop them

Tease	Frequency	Percent
Yes	30	75.0
No	10	25.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 18: Showing the negative attitude regarding hijras increase their problems

Negative attitude	Frequency	Percent
Yes	34	85.0
No	6	15.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 19: Showing that hijras positive role in society

Positive role	Frequency	Percent
Yes	24	60.0
No	16	40.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 20: Showing that the existing facilities are enough

Existing facilities	Frequency	Percent
Yes	6	15.0
No	34	85.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 21: Showing that creation is due to genetical problems

Genetically problem	Frequency	Percent
Yes	30	75.0
No	10	25.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 22: Showing their presence is the cause of poor medical facilities

Poor Medical	Frequency	Percent
Yes	22	55.0
No	18	45.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 23: Showing that they leave their area due to societal pressure

Societal Pressure	Frequency	Percent
Yes	30	75.0
No	10	25.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 24: Showing that the religion is in favour of their status

Religion favour	Frequency	Percent
Yes	20	50.0
No	20	50.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 25: Showing the wish to strengthen/ have relation with them

Relation	Frequency	Percent
Yes	10	25.0
No	30	75.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 26: Showing friendship with them they will accept them

Friendship	Frequency	Percent
Yes	16	40.0
No	24	60.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 27: Showing invitation on their celebrations

Celebration	Frequency	Percent
Yes	14	35.0
No	26	65.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 28: Showing that they are religious people

Religious people	Frequency	Percent
Yes	16	40.0
No	24	60.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 29: Showing that their birth is due to curse

Curse	Frequency	Percent
Yes	18	45.0
No	22	55.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 30: Showing emotionally hurts when they see their miserable lives

Emotionally hurt	Frequency	Percent
Yes	38	95.0
No	2	5.0
Total	40	100.0

SUMMARY

The data collected from the respondents revealed that majority of respondents (22 being 55.0%) do not want to interact with hijras while the remaining 18 (45%) interact with hijras. In considering hijras as normal individuals, 26 (65.0%) respondents of the total do not consider them as normal individuals while only 14 respondents were in positive mood regarding them. The data shows that majority of the respondents (30 being 75%) think that hijras must have equal rights like other citizens while the remaining 25% of the respondents give negative response. It was found that 22 (55.0%) respondents viewed that if they were in neighborhood, they would visit their homes while 45% of the respondents claimed that they do not visit their homes. Table 5 showed the data regarding respondents's views about hijras residency in their area, that 22 respondents (55%) claimed that if they want to take residency in their area, they will allow them, and 45% of the respondents said that they will not allow them. Further the data shows that majority of the respondents (34 being 85%) were of the view that if they need anything, they will give them, and only 6 respondents said that they will not give them anything. In table 7 majority 24 respondents (60%) think that they are adjustable people in society while the remaining 16 respondents give negative response. It was also found that 24 respondents (60%) said that they don't participate in their burials and only 16 respondents were in positive mood. All of the respondents (100%) viewed that they have right to live a respectable life in society.

In considering them deviants, 22 respondents (55%) were of the view that they are deviant while 45% claimed that they are not deviant. The data showed that the Majority of the respondents (34 being 85%) think that they dance to fulfill their financial needs and only 15% claimed that they do not dance to fulfill their financial needs. It was also found that 26 respondents being 65% claimed that they have no proper religion while 14 respondents give positive response. When the respondents were asked that whether their presence in society is according to religious injunction, majority 26 respondents being 65% of the total said that their presence in society is not according to religious injunctions and the remaining 14 respondents claimed that their presence in society is according to religious injunction. When the respondents were asked about hijras status in society that whether they have lower status in society, it was found that 32 respondents being 80% of the total were in positive mood and only 8 respondents said that they don't have a lower status in society. The data collected from the respondents revealed that most of the respondents, that is 32 being 80% said that their activities has negative effect on social environment while only 20% claimed that their activities do not have negative effect on social environment.

The data recorded from the respondents revealed that 24 respondents being 60% were of the view that they take interest in solving their problems and 40% claimed that they do not take interest in solving their problem. It was also found that most of the respondents, that is 30 being 75% argued that if anybody tease them, they try to stop them and the remaining 25% showed negative response. In table 18 majority 34 respondents being 85% of the total viewed that the negative attitude of society regarding hijras increase their problems and only 6 respondents claimed that the negative attitudes of society regarding hijras do not increase their problems. Further that data recorded from the respondents showed that majority of the respondents (24 being 60%) viewed that hijras has a positive role in society and 40% claimed that they don't have any positive role in society. As for the existing facilities regarding hijras

is concerned, majority of the respondents, that is 34 being 85% agreed that the existing facilities are not enough for them and only 6 respondents said that existing facilities are enough for them. The data shows that 30 respondent being 75% viewed that their creation is due to genetical problems of their parents while 25% said that their creation is not due to genetical problem. It was also found that 22 respondents being 55% of the total were of the view that their presence is the curse of poor medical facilities and 45% argued that their presence is not the curse of poor medical facilities. When the respondents were asked that whether the hijras left their villages due to societal pressure, most of the respondents (30 being 75% of the total) agreed that they left their villages or areas due to societal pressure and only 25% said that they did not leave their villages due to societal pressure. Further it was found that half of the total respondents, that is 20 being 50% said that religion is in favor of their status while 50% respondents give negative response. The data revealed that 30 respondent being 75% claimed that they have no wish to strengthen relation with hijras and only 25% were in positive mood. Majority 24 respondents being 60% viewed that if hijras want to make friendship with them, they will not accept them as a friend in society and 40% said that they will accept their friendship. The data in table 27 showed that 26 respondent being 65% argued that if hijras give invitation to them, they will not participate in their celebration while 13 respondents said that they will participate in their celebration. The data revealed that 24 respondents being 60% of the total viewed that they are not religious people and the remaining 40% claimed that they are religious. It was found that 22 respondents being 55% argued that their birth is not due to curse while 45% urged that their birth is curse. As for the respondents's views about the miserable life of hijras is concerned, majority of the respondents (38 being 95%) argued that they are emotionally hurt when they see their miserable lives and only 2% said that they are not hurt when they see their miserable lives.

REFERENCES

- Ali S (2003). Khawajasaraoon Ki Dunya. Nawa-e-Waqt: Sunday Magazine, p.27 and ethical perspectives, pp. 207-229). Philadelphia: Lippincott,William&Wilkins. Department of Anthropology, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan.
- Riaz H (1996). Socioeconomic organization of khusras. Unpublished M.S Dissertation.
- Sharma SK (2000). Hijras: The labelled deviance. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House.
- Talwar R (1999). The third sex and human rights. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House.